

A New Synthesis of a Naturally Occurring Isocoumarin. 3,4-Dimethyl-8-hydroxyisocoumarin (Oospolactone)

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3,4-Dimethyl-8-methoxyisochroman (5a) on oxidation furnishes 3,4-dimethyl-8-methoxy-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (6a), and demethylated with hydriodic acid to 3,4-dimethyl-8-hydroxy-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (7a). Treatment of 6a with *N*-bromosuccinimide followed by refluxing with triethylamine furnishes 3,4-dimethyl-8-methoxyisocoumarin (8a) which on demethylation with hydriodic acid yields 3,4-dimethyl-8-hydroxyisocoumarin (oospolactone) (9a). Compound 5a and 3,4-dimethyl-6-methoxyisochroman (5b) obtained by treating 3-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)butan-2-ol (4) with HCHO/HCl are separated by fractional distillation. Compound 4 is obtained from α -(*m*-methoxyphenyl)propionaldehyde (3) by Grignard reaction with methylmagnesium iodide. The aldehyde (3) is obtained from *m*-methoxyacetophenone (1) by Darzens glycidic ester condensation followed by hydrolysis and decarboxylation of the resulting product.

A new route to the synthesis of 4-alkyl- and 3,4-dialkyl-isocoumarins has recently been reported^{1,2}. Employing this route *m*-methoxyacetophenone (1), obtained from *m*-hydroxyacetophenone by methylation with Me₂SO₄/NaOH, was converted into α -(*m*-methoxyphenyl)propionaldehyde (3) via ethyl β -methyl- β -(*m*-hydroxyphenyl)glycidate (2) (Scheme 1). 2 was obtained from 1 by Darzens glycidic ester condensation and was subsequently hydrolysed followed by decarboxylation to give the aldehyde (3). Treatment of this aldehyde with methylmagnesium iodide furnished 3-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)butan-2-ol (4). 4 was taken in formalin (37%) and dry dioxane mixture and bubbling of hydrogen chloride gas through this solution at 55–60° afforded a mixture of 3,4-dimethyl-8-methoxyisochroman (5a) and 3,4-dimethyl-6-methoxyisochroman (5b), which were separated by fractional distillation under reduced pressure. Oxidation of 5a by chromium trioxide in glacial acetic acid or by selenium dioxide in boiling xylene furnished 3,4-dimethyl-8-methoxy-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (6a). Demethylation of 6a with 87% hydriodic acid gave 3,4-dimethyl-8-hydroxy-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (7a), m.p. 61–2 (lit³, 63°); it responded to the ferric chloride test and exhibited a broad ir band at 3 400–3 200 cm⁻¹ showing intramolecular hydrogen bonding of the hydroxyl with the carbonyl of the lactone ring. The dihydroisocoumarin (6a) furnished 3,4-dimethyl-8-methoxyisocoumarin (8a) on treatment with NBS in boiling carbon tetrachloride in presence of 60 W lamp followed by refluxing the 4-bromo derivative obtained after removal of the solvent with triethylamine for 3 h. Demethylation of 8a with hydriodic acid (87%) resulted in the formation of 3,4-dimethyl-8-hydroxyisocoumarin (oospolactone)

(9a), m.p. 127–28° (lit⁴, 129°), which was found to be a chelated phenol; soluble in alkali and giving a blue violet colour with ferric chloride. This compound (9) was originally isolated^{4,5} by Yamamoto and Yamamoto from the mycelium and culture filtrate of oospora, a microorganism obtained from air.

Experimental

Melting points and boiling points are uncorrected. Uv spectra were recorded on a Beckmann DK-2A spectrophotometer, ir spectra on a Perkin–Elmer spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (60 MHz) on a Varian A-60 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard.

Ethyl β -methyl- β -(m-methoxyphenyl)glycidate (2): To a mixture of *m*-methoxyacetophenone (15 g) and dry ethyl chloroacetate (12 ml) in dry benzene (40 ml), sodium ethoxide solution in ethanol (4.0 g sodium in 50 ml absolute ethanol) was added dropwise at 10–15°. After stirring the mixture for 2 h at room temperature, it was poured on crushed ice. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with benzene (3×50 ml). The organic layer and the benzene extracts were mixed, washed with water (3×50 ml) and dilute acetic acid (2.0 ml in 50 ml water) and dried (anhyd.ous Na₂SO₄). After removal of the solvent, the liquid product was distilled under reduced pressure, (24 g), b.p. 145–46°/3 mm (Found: C, 65.42; H, 7.16. C₁₇H₁₇O₄ calcd. for: C, 65.80; H, 7.22%); ν_{max} (neat) 3 030, 3 000, 2 920, 1 440, 1 380 (C–H), 1 735 (C=O of ester), 1 615, 1 585 (Ar), 1 230 (epoxy) and 1 120 cm⁻¹ (methoxy).

α -(m-Methoxyphenyl) propionaldehyde (3): Ethyl β -methyl- β -(*m*-methoxyphenyl)glycidate (20.0 g) was

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) $\text{ClCH}_2\text{COOEt}$, (ii) OEt , (iii) aqueous NaOH , (iv) MeMgI , (v) HCHO/HCl , (vi) fractional distillation, (vii) CrO_3 or SeO_2 , (viii) HI , (ix) $\text{NBS-Et}_3\text{N}$, (x) HI .

added to a stirred solution of sodium hydroxide (35.0 g) in water (75 ml) and the stirring continued for 2 h at 55–60° resulting in a clear homogeneous liquid which on cooling solidified, which was acidified to congo red with hydrochloric acid (6*N*), heated for 1 h on a water-bath with the evolution of carbon dioxide and finally separation of an oil. After cooling, the oil was extracted with benzene (3×40 ml), and the combined benzene extract washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). After removal of the solvent a clear liquid was obtained which was distilled under reduced pressure, (9.5 g), b.p. 105–7°/3 mm (Found : C, 72.90; H, 7.12. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$ calcd. for : C, 73.14; H, 7.37%); ν_{max}

(neat) 3 030, 2 990, 2 920, 1 735, 1 600, 1 585, 1 440, 1 380 and 1 110 cm^{-1} .

3-(*m*-Methoxyphenyl)butan-2-ol (4) : *o*-(*m*-Methoxyphenyl)propionaldehyde (8.1 g) in dry ether (25 ml) was added to the Grignard solution (prepared from 3.0 g Mg and 15 g MeI in 25 ml dry ether) with stirring and was refluxed for 1 h. The ethereal solution was then poured onto crushed ice, acidified with dilute H_2SO_4 and extracted with ether (2×25 ml). The ether extract was washed with dilute NaHCO_3 solution and water and dried (anhydrous K_2CO_3). Removal of the solvent gave a residue which was distilled under reduced pressure, (14 g), b.p. 118–20°/2 mm (Found : C, 73.15; H, 8.85. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ calcd. for : C, 73.29; H, 8.95%); ν_{max} (clear) 3 450 (OH), 3 090, 3 000, 2 950, 1 480, 1 400 (C–H), 1 615 (Ar) and 1 110 cm^{-1} (MeO).

3,4-Dimethyl-6-methoxyisochroman (5b) and 3,4-dimethyl-8-methoxyisochroman (5a) : Dry HCl gas bubbled in a solution of 5 (10 g), formalin (10 ml), concentrated HCl (0.5 ml) and dry dioxane (15 ml) for 2 h at such a rate that temperature of the mixture remained 55–65°. After cooling, it was poured into ice-water and extracted with ether (3×40 ml). The ether extract was washed with aqueous Na_2CO_3 and water, and dried (fused CaCl_2). After removal of the solvent, the residual liquid was distilled under reduced pressure to furnish two fractions. Fraction-I was identified as 3,4-dimethyl-6-methoxyisochroman, (5b; 3.6 g), b.p. 109°/2 mm (Found : C, 74.91; H, 8.12. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ calcd. for : C, 74.96; H, 8.39%); λ_{max} 245 and 275 nm; ν_{max} (neat) 3 015, 2 900, 1 425, 1 400 (C–H), 1 120, 1 090 (etheral) and 1 606 cm^{-1} (Ar); δ (CCl_4) 1.31 (6H, m, $\text{C}_3\text{-CH}_3$ and $\text{C}_4\text{-CH}_3$), 2.55 (1H, m, H-3), 3.60 (1H, m, H-4), 4.45 (2H, s, H-1), 3.60 (3H, s, $\text{C}_6\text{-OCH}_3$) and 8.05 (3H, m, Ar). Fraction-II was identified as 3,4-dimethyl-8-methoxyisochroman (5a; 1.3 g), b.p. 126°/2 mm (Found : C, 74.82; H, 8.34. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ calcd. for : C, 74.96; H, 8.39%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 247 and 272 nm; ν_{max} (neat) 3 000, 2 905, 1 420, 1 330 (C–H), 1 125, 1 100 (etheral) and 1 610 cm^{-1} (Ar); δ (CCl_4) 1.30 (6H, m, $\text{C}_3\text{-CH}_3$ and $\text{C}_4\text{-CH}_3$), 2.70 (1H, m, H-3), 3.65 (1H, m, H-4), 4.60 (2H, s, H-1), 3.75 (3H, s, $\text{C}_6\text{-OCH}_3$) and 7.95 (3H, m, Ar).

3,4-Dimethyl-8-methoxy 3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (6a) : (i) A solution of chromium trioxide (3.0 g) in water (5 ml) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was added with stirring to 3,4-dimethyl-8-methoxyisochroman (5a; 1.0 g) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) at room temperature. The reaction was exothermic and it was cooled occasionally by ice to maintain the temperature at 25–30°. It was stirred for 2 h at room temperature, then mixed with an equal volume of water and extracted with chloroform. The extract was washed with aqueous Na_2CO_3 (10%) and water, and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent gave a gummy solid which was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°)¹⁰

afford 3,4-dimethyl-8-methoxy-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin as prisms (0.55 g), m.p. 74–5° (Found: C, 69.58; H, 6.72. $C_{11}H_{14}O_3$ calcd for: C, 69.88; H, 6.84%).

(ii) A solution of 5a (1.0 g) in xylene (20 ml) was treated with freshly prepared selenium dioxide (1.8 g) and refluxed for 8 h. The hot reaction mixture was filtered and the resulting gummy residue after removal of the solvent was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over neutral alumina (30 g), eluting the column with the same solvent. After removal of the solvent a residue was obtained which on crystallisation from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) afforded 3,4-dimethyl-8-methoxy-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (0.45 g) as prisms (0.45 g); m.m.p. of the specimen obtained by methods (i) and (ii) showed no depression, thus identical with the specimen obtained in method (i); λ_{max} (EtOH) 245 and 280 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 090, 2 900, 1 450, 1 395 (C–H), 1 735 (C=O of lactone), 1 105 (etheral) and 1 595 cm^{-1} (Ar); δ (CCl₄) 1.38 (6H, m, C₂-CH₃ and C₄-CH₃), 2.95 (1H, m, H-3), 4.45 (1H, m, H-4), 3.85 (3H, s, C₈-OCH₃), 8.05 (1H, m, H-7) and 7.75 (2H, m, Ar).

3,4-Dimethyl-8-hydroxy-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (7a): A mixture of 6a (0.25 g) and freshly distilled hydriodic acid (7 ml, 57%) was refluxed for 3 h. After removal of hydriodic acid, it was cooled, extracted with ether, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvent was removed and the residue crystallised from ethyl acetate–petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) to afford 3,4-dimethyl-8-hydroxy-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin as needles, (0.16 g) m.p. 61–2° (lit.⁸ 63°) (Found: C, 68.69; H, 6.25. $C_{11}H_{14}O_3$ calcd. for: C, 68.73; H, 6.9%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 240 and 285 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 200–3 400 (OH), 3 000, 2 910, 1 450, 1 410 (C–H), 1 740 (C=O of lactone) and 1 605 cm^{-1} (Ar).

3,4-Dimethyl-8-methoxyisocoumarin (8a): A mixture of 3,4-dimethyl-8-methoxy-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (0.4 g), *N* bromosuccinimide (2.1 g) in dry CCl₄ (50 ml) was refluxed for 2.5 h, the reaction flask being kept close to a 60 W lamp. The reaction mixture was then cooled and filtered and

the filtrate washed with aqueous sodium carbonate (5%) and water, and dried (Na₂SO₄). After removal of the solvent on a water-bath, the residue was refluxed with triethylamine (40 ml) for 6 h and the gummy residue left after removal of triethylamine was triturated repeatedly with ice-cold HCl (2*N*) followed by water. It was then taken in petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), washed again with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvent was removed and the residual oil solidified on long standing and then crystallised from n-hexane as colourless needles (0.25 g), m.p. 141–42° (Found: C, 70.51; H, 5.82. $C_{11}H_{14}O_3$ calcd. for: C, 70.57; H, 5.92%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 275 and 320 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 005, 2 910, 1 420, 1 390 (C–H), 1 740 (C=O of lactone), 1 615, 1 600 (Ar) and 1 110 cm^{-1} (etheral); δ (CCl₄) 2.35 (3H, s, C₄-CH₃), 2.15 (3H, s, C₂-CH₃), 4.12 (3H, s, C₈-OCH₃), 7.95 (1H, m, Ar) and 7.30 (2H, m, Ar).

3,4-Dimethyl-8-hydroxyisocoumarin (9a): A mixture of 7a (0.15 g) and freshly distilled hydriodic acid (5 ml, 57%) was refluxed for 3 h. After removal of the hydriodic acid, it was cooled, extracted with ether, washed with saturated NaHCO₃ solution and water, and dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvent was then removed and the solid residue crystallised from ethyl acetate to give 3,4-dimethyl-8-hydroxyisocoumarin (0.09 g), m.p. 127–8° (lit.⁴, 129°; synthesised earlier by a different route⁹) (Found: C, 69.91; H, 5.26. $C_{11}H_{14}O_3$ calcd. for: C, 69.49; H, 5.30%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 260 and 325 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 200–3 425 (OH), 2 990, 2 910, 1 745, 1 610, 1 600, 1 425 and 1 400 cm^{-1} .

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